

Title: Supplementary Material for the manuscript “SensitiveCancerGPT: Generative AI for Actionable Pharmacogenomics in Precision Oncology”

1. Drug sensitivity tabular data

Drug	Cell Line	Response
topotecan	hcc1806	Sensitive

2. Convert tabular input to conversation chat format

```
{ "messages": [ { "role": "user", "content": "Decide in a single word if the drug response to the cell line is sensitive or resistant. The drug is topotecan and the cell line is hcc1806: " }, { "role": "assistant", "content": "sensitive" } ] }
```

3. Predict drug response

Supplementary Figure S1. Example of the conversation-style input formatting used to construct training samples for LLM fine-tuning. Each drug–cell line instance is serialized as a structured dialogue to align with chat-based LLM interfaces.

(A) Instruction Prompt

**"Decide in a single word if the drug response is sensitive or resistant.
The drug name is daporinad. The cell line is vmrc-lcd. Drug response: sensitive
The drug name is uprosertib. The cell line is nci-h1693. Drug response: resistant
The drug name is bortezomib. The cell line is lc-2-ad. Drug response:"**

(B) Instruction-Prefix Prompt

**"Decide in a single word if the drug response is sensitive or resistant.
Drug name: daporinad; cell line: vmrc-lcd; drug response: sensitive
Drug name: uprosertib; cell line: nci-h1693; drug response: resistant
Drug name: bortezomib; cell line: lc-2-ad; drug response:"**

(C) Cloze Prompt

**"The cell line vmrc-lcd is sensitive to the drug daporinad.
The cell line nci-h1693 is resistant to the drug uprosertib.
The cell line lc-2-ad is [Z] to the drug bortezomib."**

Supplementary Figure S2. Representative examples of prompt templates used for few-shot evaluation, illustrating variations in instruction phrasing and contextual structure.

1. Drug sensitivity tabular data

Drug	Cell Line	Gene Mutation	Response
bortezomib	hcc2157	aard,eif3h,rad21,slc30a8,trps1,utp23 arhgef10 csmd1 rcbtb2	sensitive

2. Convert tabular input to natural language text T

"The drug name is bortezomib. The cell line is hcc2157.
The gene mutation is aard,eif3h,rad21,slc30a8,trps1,utp23 arhgef10 csmd1
rcbtb2.
Drug response:"

3. Prepare a task-specific instruction I and concatenate with T to get the final prompt P

"Decide in a single word if the drug response is sensitive or resistant.
The drug name is bortezomib. The cell line is hcc2157.
The gene mutation is aard,eif3h,rad21,slc30a8,trps1,utp23 arhgef10 csmd1
rcbtb2.
Drug response:"

4. Predict drug response

Supplementary Figure S3A. Example input prompt incorporating biological information and molecular genomic context (BI + MGC) from the GDSC dataset.

1. Drug sensitivity tabular data

Drug	Cell Line	Gene Expression	Response
panobinostat	nci-h1915	gapdh rps17 rps24 rps11 mt-nd3 tmsb10	sensitive

2. Convert tabular input to natural language text T

"The drug name is panobinostat. The cell line is nci-h1915.
The gene expression is gapdh rps17 rps24 rps11 mt-nd3 tmsb10
Drug response:"

3. Prepare a task-specific instruction I and concatenate with T to get the final prompt P

"Decide in a single word if the drug response is sensitive or resistant.
The drug name is panobinostat. The cell line is nci-h1915.
The gene expression is gapdh rps17 rps24 rps11 mt-nd3 tmsb10
Drug response:"

4. Predict drug response

Supplementary Figure S3B. Example input prompt incorporating biological information and molecular genomic context (BI + MGC) from the CCLE dataset. Portions of gene expression features are truncated with ellipses for brevity.

1. Drug sensitivity tabular data

Drug	Cell Line	Drug-Drug Synergy	Response
topotecan	sw900	synergistic with drug navitoclax	sensitive

2. Convert tabular input to natural language text T

"The drug name is topotecan. The cell line is sw900.
The drug is synergistic with drug navitoclax.
Drug response:"

3. Prepare a task-specific instruction I and concatenate with T to get the final prompt P

"Decide in a single word if the drug response is sensitive or resistant.
The drug name is topotecan. The cell line is sw900.
The drug is synergistic with drug navitoclax.
Drug response:"

4. Predict drug response

Supplementary Figure S3C. Example input prompt incorporating biological information and molecular genomic context (BI + MGC) from the DrugComb dataset.

1. Drug sensitivity tabular data

Drug	Cell Line	Drug's Mechanism of Action	Response
panobinostat	ncih1435	hdac inhibitor	sensitive

2. Convert tabular input to natural language text T

"The drug name is panobinostat. The cell line is ncih1435.
The drug's mechanism of action is hdac inhibitor.
Drug response:"

3. Prepare a task-specific instruction I and concatenate with T to get the final prompt P

"Decide in a single word if the drug response is sensitive or resistant.
The drug name is panobinostat. The cell line is ncih1435.
The drug's mechanism of action is hdac inhibitor.
Drug response:"

4. Predict drug response

Supplementary Figure S3D. Example input prompt incorporating drug descriptors, biological information, and molecular genomic context (Drug + BI + MGC) from the PRISM dataset.

Supplementary Figure S4. Performance comparison of different learning paradigms (e.g., zero-shot, few-shot, fine-tuning) across datasets, stratified by tissue type.

Supplementary Figure S5. Performance comparison of different prompt templates across datasets, stratified by tissue type.

Supplementary Figure S6. Performance evaluation of different feature combinations (e.g., BI, BI+MS, BI+MGC) across datasets, stratified by tissue type.

Supplementary Figure S7. Baseline performance comparison between GPT-3 and representative language model baselines across datasets.

Supplementary Figure S8. Baseline performance comparison between SensitiveCancerGPT (GPT-3 backbone) and representative drug response prediction models.